

Supporting Information

Lithium Intercalation in the Anisotropic van der Waals Semiconductor CrSBr

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Supplementary Section 1. Optical Contrast Techniques to Estimate the Thickness of CrSBr.

Optical contrast is a well-established method for estimating the thickness of two-dimensional materials in white-light microscopy.^[1–3] This technique, commonly applied to graphene, hBN, and TMDCs flakes on SiO₂/Si substrate allows for thickness estimation as a function of their color.^[4,5] Figure S1 displays the optical images of mechanically exfoliated bulk crystals with corresponding profile data details. A visible color shift from violet-blue to yellow and grayish-pink indicates changes in flake thickness, as reflected in the developed color scale.

In accordance with the group theory, Raman scattering spectra of CrSBr at 532 nm excitation exhibit the three active phonon modes (A_g , B_{2g} , B_{3g}) observable at room temperature. Among them, the main optical phonons are those of A_g symmetry. Atomic displacements of the A_g^1 , A_g^2 , A_g^3 modes correspond to out-of-plane vibrations of chromium, sulfur, and bromine atoms, respectively. Considering the anisotropic nature of CrSBr, we co-polarized the excitation along the crystalline b axis. Thus, we observe out-of-plane A_g^1 , A_g^2 , and A_g^3 modes with the frequency of 114 cm^{-1} , 244 cm^{-1} , 342 cm^{-1} for mechanically exfoliated CrSBr (Figure S1d). Remarkably, the Raman spectra do not differentiate the thickness of all selected flakes with the number of layers $N > 10$.

Figure S1. Characterization of exfoliated CrSBr. (a) Optical micrograph of ca. 8 nm thick flake exhibiting a violet blue color. (b) Ca. 25 nm and ca. 35 nm thick flakes exhibiting a bright blue and sky-blue color, respectively. (c) Multilayered flake with increasing thickness values from ca. 65 nm to more than ca. 90

nm manifested by different colors from yellow to grayish pink. (d) Raman spectra of selected flakes of different thickness. The color scale for rough thickness estimation is presented in the middle. Corresponding AFM micrographs and line scan profile 1 of (a) ca. 8 nm thick flake, profile 2 and 3 of (b) ca. 20 nm and ca. 30 nm thick flakes, respectively, and profiles 4 and 5 of (c) multilayered flake with a thickness of ca. 65 nm and 90 nm, respectively.

Figure S2. Optical micrographs of the solvated electron solution. (a) Lithium anthracenide in THF at the onset of the reaction, when thin plates of metallic lithium are added to the mixture and (b) after stabilization, when the reaction is completed and all lithium dissolved, the solution turns a saturated deep blue. The stock solution (32 mM lithium anthracenide) appears dark blue, as shown in micrographs (b) and (c). In micrograph (c), the diluted stock solutions (0.64 mM and 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide) exhibit a brilliant blue and a transparent appearance, respectively.

Supplementary Section 2. Secondary-ion mass spectrometry for the study of lithium intercalation.

Since lithium compounds are challenging to analyze utilizing conventional EDX spectroscopy techniques due to the low characteristic X-ray signal of lithium, even with a windowless detector, we employed time-of-flight secondary-ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS) technique. This method relies on sputtering the sample's surface with a beam of primary ions and detecting the mass of secondary ions formed during the sputtering process^[6], confirming the successful intercalation of Li into CrSBr structure and highlighting the presence of lithium within the depth of material.

Secondary ion intensity can be expressed by a value that accounts for the complex matrix effects and sputtering conditions:

$$I_s = I_p Y R^\mp c^{\text{surf}} T \quad (\text{S1})$$

where I_p is the primary ion current, Y is the sputtering yield, R^\mp is the ionization probability, c^{surf} is the fractional concentration of the element in the surface, and T is a mass spectrometer transmission. However, applying identical acquisition conditions, matrix effect of the studied material, and the same settings of mass spectrum (MS), we can assume a simplified equation:

$$I_s = X(I_p, Y, R^\mp, T) c^{\text{surf}} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where X is a combined constant, which is the same among all the measurements for every specific mass (note, that there is no correlation between various masses). Under these assumptions, we can determine the relative change in concentration both in lateral sizes (top view) and in depth profile.

We prepare the sample of mechanically exfoliated CrSBr on a silicon substrate coated with a 250 nm-thick gold layer to avoid electron charge accumulation on the wafer, since the electrons recombine with ions and therefore, a significant loss of the MS signal is observed. The wafers with mechanically exfoliated CrSBr were characterized using optical, Raman, and AFM, then immersed in 0.32mM lithium anthracenide solution for 15 minutes to perform the intercalation. Figure S3 presents optical micrographs, which provide an overview of the pristine and intercalated material. Based on the observed color, we concluded that flakes 1 and 2 possess similar thicknesses, whereas flake 3 is significantly thicker. This observation is confirmed by the AFM analysis. The thickness of flake 1 is approximately 15 nm, flake 2 is 20 nm, and flake 3 is 70 nm, with a thicker edge measuring ~120 nm (indicated by the red, green, and blue profiles in the optical image inset, respectively). Raman spectra presented in Figure S3a-c confirmed that complete intercalation was achieved for the thin flakes (1 and 2) exhibiting the low-energy vibrational mode A_1^1 , while the thicker flake (3) was partially intercalated.

Figure S3. Optical image of pristine exfoliated CrSBr with AFM profiles of marked flakes 1-3 shown in the inset. Optical image of intercalated flakes with a marked by a blue dotted rectangle area chosen for SIMS analysis ($30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$). (a–c) Raman spectra of pristine and intercalated flakes 1–3.

Secondary ions masses generated from the intercalated sample were detected at a given polarity (positive and negative) while maintaining the same settings for the primary Ga^+ source, which ensured a consistent sputtering rate. Although lithium is easily ionized due to its high ionization probability, resulting in a strong signal, the matrix effect poses significant challenges for quantifying lithium ions without suitable standards, such as implanted elements within the same matrix.^[7] Consequently, both lithium (the element of interest) and chromium (the material element) intensities were observed in the positive ion elemental mapping, as the inherently measured signals under identical acquisition conditions served as a relative concentration of the specific element.

The schematics in Figure S4a illustrate the principles of SIMS analysis. First, we collected the signal from regions of 100×100 pixels within a field of view of $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ to fairly represent lithium distribution within the sample. Once primary ionization was initiated, Li-CrSBr was analyzed frame by frame, while the secondary ion masses generated from increasing sputtered depths were detected. This spectroscopy method is destructive, as sputtering etches both the material and the substrate at the same rate, as depicted in the SEM micrographs of the initial and analyzed samples in Figure S4b,e. The resulting positive secondary ion image maps ($30 \mu\text{m} \times 30 \mu\text{m}$) in Figure 4c,d,f, g display the elemental distribution of Li and Cr across the area of interest. The color indicates the number of selected species emitted per pixel within the analyzed area, ensuring both Li and Cr are present. Additionally, the positive ion mass spectral data shows all isotopes of Cr and Li and indicates the signals of lithium ($m/z=7$) and chromium ($m/z=52$) with

their intensities an order of magnitude higher than those of environmental sodium and potassium, as presented in Figure S4h.

Figure S4. Secondary-ion mass spectrometry implementation. (a) Schematic illustration of SIMS principals. SEM micrographs of initial (b) and analyzed (e) sample taken before and after spectrometry, respectively. The secondary ion image maps of elemental chromium and lithium represented in top (c, d) and front (f, g) projections. (h) Secondary ions mass spectrum of Li-CrSBr collected from whole ($30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$) area. (i) Elemental depth profiles of Li (7) and Cr (52) collected from $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ and limited $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ areas of interest. (j) Limited to $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ area of interest.

Although lithium and chromium exhibit strong signals within the 100 frames, as illustrated in the front projection maps in Figure S4f,g, their intensities evolve distinctly as sputtering progresses. However, the view field of $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ spans not only the intercalated CrSBr flakes but also the wafer itself, which affects the resulting front projection maps. Thus, we limited the area of interest to $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ to ultimately represent the element depth analysis from the intercalated material. The considered area is presented in Figure S4j. The element depth analysis of the limited area seen in Figure S4i shows that elemental intensities of Li and Cr are in the same order of magnitude with an increase within the slight penetration, which evidence the ultimate presence of Li within the CrSBr crystalline structure. Notably, the lithium profile stabilizes shortly after sputtering begins, in contrast to the depth profile obtained from the $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ view field. After 200 frames, both Cr and Li signals are significantly weakened manifesting the etching and destruction of the investigated material. Upon completion of the scan, we quantified the penetration depth based on

the intensity of the Cr signal and the known thickness of the investigated flake measured by AFM. Since the depth profile was collected from flake 2 with a known thickness of 20 nm, we conclude that 1 nm of material is etched within 10 sputtering frames.

By surveying a series of intercalation conditions, we find that a 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide solution (15 min immersion) leads to the Li/Cr secondary-ion ratio within the same order of magnitude. As expected, the highest lithium intensity was observed for the Li-CrSBr treated with 0.45 mM lithium anthracenide, however, the signal of Cr was lower by an order of magnitude compared to Li, while lower lithium anthracenide concentration (0.2 mM) resulted in incomplete intercalation.

To investigate the influence of 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide on the intensity of secondary ion masses generated from the intercalated sample, we further acquired the SIMS signal from the sample treated with an abundance and deficiency of lithium ions. Figure S5 illustrates the variations in the intensities of the element of interest (Li) and the material element (Cr) as a function of the lithium anthracenide concentration used for intercalation. The data points were extracted from the elemental depth profiles of 13 samples after 10 seconds of sputtering, with the considered area of $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$, covering exclusively the surface of the material.

The analysis of the samples treated with 0.45 mM lithium anthracenide revealed the highest lithium intensity, with the intensities of Li (7) and Cr (52) differing by 7.23 ± 2.26 cts. Conversely, the sample treated with 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide exhibited the smallest intensity ratio between Li (7) and Cr (52), calculated as 0.57 ± 0.24 cts, and represented by overlapping data points in Figure S5. A deficiency of lithium ions, achieved by treatment with 0.2 mM lithium anthracenide, resulted in a weaker lithium signal, with an intensity ratio between Li (7) and Cr (52) of 0.33 ± 0.24 cts. Collectively, these findings establish a trend between the generated secondary ion masses and the concentration of lithium anthracenide used, confirming the Raman study findings claiming 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide is the “optimum” concentration for 15 minutes of CrSBr intercalation.

Figure S5. The variations in the intensities of the element of interest (Li) and the material element (Cr) as a function of the lithium anthracenide concentration.

Supplementary Section 3. Lithium Intercalation into Exfoliated CrSBr: Concentration Experiment.

Figure S6 presents optical micrographs and Raman spectra of exfoliated CrSBr flakes before and after lithium intercalation. On each wafer, eight flakes with varying colors, ranging from violet-blue (thin) to grayish-yellow (thick), were selected to represent different thicknesses, labeled 1 through 8 accordingly.

To assess whether anthracene in THF affects the CrSBr structure, we first conducted a control experiment using a blank solution (no lithium, no solvated electrons). As shown in Figure S6a, the optical appearance of the flakes remained unchanged, and Raman spectra (Figure S6f) showed no shifts in the A_g^1 , A_g^2 , and A_g^3 modes (114 , 244 , and 342 cm^{-1} , respectively). All peaks exhibited clean Lorentzian line shapes, from which we extracted peak positions and FWHM values (plotted as error bars).

We started with 0.2 mM lithium anthracenide (32 mM stock diluted by factor of 150) for CrSBr intercalation. At this concentration, the solution appeared notably transparent. As seen in Figure S6b, thicker flakes darkened slightly around the edges. Figure S6g illustrates the frequency positions of the A_g^1 , A_g^2 , A_g^3 modes, where solid-colored spheres are original peak positions, and semi-transparent spheres depict the data from Li-CrSBr. Intercalated flakes 1-4 with a thickness of ca. 30 nm exhibit A_1^1 , A_1^2 , A_1^3 modes at 95 cm^{-1} , 225 cm^{-1} , and 334 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicated by the dashed line in Figure S6g. Additionally, the FWHM values of the intercalated flakes are broadened, which is shown by the error bars.

Figure S6. Concentration series experiment: optical micrographs of the exfoliated flakes before and after lithium anthracene treatment with (a) blank with no lithium and varying concentration of (b) 0.2 mM, (c) 0.32 mM, (d) 0.45 mM, and (e) 0.64 mM lithium anthracene. (f–j) Raman mode positions as a function of flake number marked on the corresponding optical micrographs.

To gain further insight, we analyzed the intercalation using a 0.32 mM lithium anthracenide solution (stock diluted by a factor of 100), which remarkably remained transparent. Optical images presented in Figure S6c reveal minimal changes in thin flakes (1–3), with a mild darkening, while thicker flakes (6–8) displayed increased contrast at the edges. Importantly, all flakes remain present, with no external morphological changes visible. Raman analysis of Li-CrSBr flakes 1–3 with a thickness of ca. 30 nm in Figure S6h confirmed A_1^1, A_1^2, A_1^3 modes at frequencies of approximately $95\text{ cm}^{-1}, 219\text{ cm}^{-1},$ and 331 cm^{-1} , respectively. The FWHM of the Li-CrSBr flakes are broadened, with FWHM of 14 cm^{-1} for Li-CrSBr and FWHM of 4 cm^{-1} for CrSBr, as shown by the error bars in Figure S6h.

Figure S7. Raman spectra of exfoliated CrSBr before (pristine), and after intercalation of ca. 30 nm thick flake 1 and ca. 70 nm thick flake 6. Silicon peak at 520 cm^{-1} originates from the substrate.

Figure S7a shows the Raman spectra of a representative fully intercalated flake with deconvoluted A_1^1, A_1^2, A_1^3 modes, picturing a shift in the A_g modes frequency positions together with a notable intensity decrease. The Raman spectra of a partially intercalated flake with a thickness of ca. 70 nm, presented in Figure S7b, reveal two distinct sets of phonon atomic displacement modes, indicating the presence of both intercalated and non-intercalated material within the illuminated area. Similar phenomena were noticed for the 0.2 mM lithium anthracenide, where we observed partial intercalation of the flakes thicker than 30 nm. In contrast, flake 8 remained unaffected (Figure S6h), with no A_1 modes detected.

Intercalation with 0.45 mM lithium anthracenide solution (stock diluted by factor of 75) demonstrated the excess of lithium, reflected at first in the distinctions in the optical images taken before and after the experiment (Figure S6d). Upon intercalation, flakes 1–4 turned bright blue, flakes 5–6 showed edge darkening, and flakes 7–8 were no longer present. Notably, the morphology of the flakes marked by dashed rectangles was altered: the thin flakes appear distorted, and part of the thicker flake is bent over. Raman spectra of flakes 1 and 2 reveal that A_1^1, A_1^2, A_1^3 modes consistently appear at frequencies of approximately $95\text{ cm}^{-1}, 217\text{ cm}^{-1},$ and 330 cm^{-1} , respectively, corresponding to Raman shifts of $19\text{ cm}^{-1}, 27\text{ cm}^{-1},$ and 12 cm^{-1} from original

values. Furthermore, the Li-CrSBr FWHM values resulted in even greater FWHM broadening of 15 cm^{-1} in comparison with FWHM of 4 cm^{-1} for CrSBr, shown by error bars in Figure S6i. Moreover, Raman spectra of flakes 3 and 4 show two phonon atomic displacement modes consistent with previously reported values for A_g and A_1 displacements. This behavior differs from thicker flakes 5 and 6, which remain structurally preserved, showing the frequency positions of the A_g^1, A_g^2, A_g^3 modes on the same positions.

To further investigate the effect of excess lithium, we used 0.64 mM lithium anthracenide in THF (stock diluted by a factor of 50). We note that solution exhibits a bright blue color. This reagent concentration significantly affects the appearance and crystalline structure of exfoliated CrSBr, as evidenced by the optical images captured before and after lithiation (Figure S6e). The intercalation with an excess of lithium causes irreversible changes in the crystalline structure of CrSBr flakes, thus, A_g vibrational modes are not clearly observed in the Raman spectra of treated flakes (Figures S6j and S8).

Figure S8. Optical micrograph after intercalation and Raman spectra of exfoliated CrSBr after the process (damaged). Due to the excess of the intercalant, the investigated flake loses its crystallinity, resulting in the suppressed frequency vibrations of A_g modes. Silicon peak at 520 cm^{-1} originates from the substrate.

Figure S9. DFT calculated optical phonon modes for pristine CrSBr and Li_{0.5}-CrSBr.

Supplementary Section 4. Stability of intercalated flake.

For the thin flake, we first acquired optical micrographs (Figure S10a) and Raman spectra (Figure S10b) of the pristine CrSBr flake, and measured the height profile by AFM (Figure S10c–d), which confirms an initial thickness of ≈ 6 nm. After 30 min of intercalation, the Raman spectrum (Figure S10b) shows that the modes of pristine CrSBr diminish, and a new set of peaks appears at lower wavenumber, characteristic of Li–CrSBr. AFM reveals pronounced wrinkles and cracks on the surface of the intercalated flake (Figure S10c with a magnified version in Figure S12a), and the corresponding line scan (Figure S10d) shows an increased thickness of ≈ 9 nm, demonstrating that intercalation leads to an increase in the flake’s thickness.

Then, we tested the structural stability of the intercalated thin flake over a 14-day period. The flake was stored in an Ar-filled glovebox, and Raman spectra were repeatedly acquired from the center of the flake. As shown in Fig. S10a, the optical appearance of the flake remains unchanged over this period. Two days after intercalation, the A_1 vibrational modes become more pronounced and more symmetric, and thereafter the spectra remain essentially unchanged (Figure S10b), indicating good structural stability of Li–CrSBr in an inert atmosphere.

Figure S10. The optical images (a), Raman spectra (b), AFM micrographs (c), and line scan profiles (d) of a pristine and intercalated CrSBr flake.

Next, we acquired the Raman spectrum (Figure S11a) and corresponding optical micrographs (Figure S11b) of a pristine CrSBr “thick” flake and examined its height profile via AFM measurement, which confirmed the thickness of ca. 40 nm (see corresponding AFM micrograph

and line scan profile in Figure S11c-d). We then deliberately intercalated the flake only partially to probe how intercalation proceeds from the edges. In this context, “partial intercalation” or “partial saturation” refers to a state in which the edges of the flake are Li⁺-rich while the center remains mostly pristine, giving rise to a Li⁺ concentration gradient across the flake. During subsequent equilibration, Li⁺ diffuses toward the center, gradually homogenizing the concentration profile.

The Raman spectrum in Figure S11a shows that over 10 minutes of intercalation, we achieved the partial flake’s saturation, where the edges of the flake are fully saturated, which was confirmed by Raman spectroscopy (see corresponding Raman spectra in Figure S11a-2). The spectrum probed from the middle part of the flake reveals two sets of phonon modes, A_g and an onset of A₁¹, which is indicative of the presence of both intercalated and non-intercalated material within the area we probe. AFM images reveal cracks after intercalation, and the intercalation pathways can be followed in Figure S11c, with a magnified version in Figure S12b. The corresponding line profile (Figure S11d) shows that the intercalated edges reach a thickness of ≈ 75 nm, while the central region is ≈ 55 nm thick. These data demonstrate that intercalation increases the thickness of the flake, starting from the edges and progressing inward via diffusion, as discussed in the corresponding section of the main text. The apparent “thinning” or “re-layering” in the optical images actually corresponds to edge “swelling” due to Li⁺ uptake rather than delamination or loss of material.

Upon storage for 14 days in an inert atmosphere, we observe that the edge spectra become slightly less Li-rich, reflected in a small shift of the A₁ modes back to higher wavenumbers. The spectrum recorded from the flake center (spectrum 5) exhibits more symmetric vibrational peaks and a more pronounced A₁¹ mode, indicating further equilibration of Li⁺ toward the interior. The AFM line profile of the 14-day-stabilized flake shows that the edges have flattened and the Li-saturated region has broadened, yielding a more uniform overall thickness of ≈ 60 nm.

Figure S11. Raman spectra (a), optical images (b), AFM micrographs (c), and line scan profiles (d) of a pristine and partially equilibrated CrSBr flake.

In both flakes, AFM reveals features which are not immediately visible in the optical micrograph. For thin flakes we observe wrinkles, most likely as a result flakes partially lifting and shifting during the intercalation process (blue arrows in Figure S12a). These can occur in any direction,

follow straight or curved paths and also branch out. In addition, we observe less pronounced, straight line-like protrusions following exclusively the a -direction (black arrows in Figure S12a-b). These may be an indication of microscopic cracks and tears forming within the structure as a result of mechanical stress during intercalation. Since chemical bonds are weaker in the b -direction, they tend to break more easily and cause the material to partially delaminate into narrow ribbons aligned with the a -direction.^[8]

Figure S12. AFM micrographs of a “thin” (a) and “thick” (b) CrSBr flakes after intercalation. The arrows indicate features which were not visible in the optical micrographs (see S10 and S11). Blue arrows show large wrinkles of the flake. Black arrows indicate line-like features most likely related to microscopic cracks and tears within the structure. Lattice orientations were determined from polarized Raman measurements.

Supplementary Section 5. Effects of partial and full hBN encapsulation.

In the process of studying the intercalation dynamics in Li-CrSBr we fabricated several flakes of CrSBr either fully or partially intercalated with hBN and investigated how this affects the intercalation process. In Figure S13b and e, two CrSBr bulk flakes are shown. The flake in Figure S13b is fully encapsulated in hBN, while Figure S13e is only partially encapsulated with one end of the flake sticking out along the a -direction. Both heterostructures were fabricated on the same chip and intercalated together at the same time. After 38 min of intercalation the first flake is still in perfect condition without any change in appearance as shown in Figure S13c, and no change in the Raman signal shown in Figure S13a before and after the treatment (the difference in relative peak intensity is due to a difference in laser polarization angel during the measurement). From this, we can conclude that full hBN encapsulation is able to protect CrSBr from intercalation. No Li was able to penetrate through the hBN in the put of plane direction or slip underneath to reach the CrSBr flake.

The second flake on the other hand is strongly intercalated especially on the edges but throughout the whole length of the sheet in the a -direction as seen in Figure S13f and confirmed by the before and after Raman measurement in Figure S13d. From this, we can conclude that if Li is able to enter a flake it will easily diffuse within the flake along the a -direction and spread even underneath the hBN cover. This already serves as an indication that a is the fast direction of diffusion.

Figure S13: (a) Raman measurement before and after intercalation. (b) Pristine CrSBr flake, fully encapsulated in hBN. (c) Flake after treatment, with no visible signs of intercalation. (d) Raman measurement before and after intercalation (taken at the edge of the flake). (e) Pristine CrSBr flake, partially encapsulated in hBN (along a -direction). (f) Flake after treatment, with visible signs of intercalation along the whole length of the flake.

In Figure S14a, another CrSBr flake is shown, again partially covered by hBN, however, this time the part of it was uncovered along the b -direction. During 2h of intercalation we observed the

intercalation progress slowly into the covered part of the sheet originating from the uncovered area, however in contrast to the previous experiment we do not see the Li diffuse quickly deep into the sheet. Instead, we observed a slow and gradual process with a sharp border between the intercalated and non-intercalated area. In Figure S14b, the flake is shown before and after the intercalation together with a Raman map indicating that the lower part of the flake was fully intercalated. The gradual progress during the intercalation is shown in Figure S14d.

The experiment was conducted with bottom contacted Au source and drain contacts to study how partially intercalating a flake will influence its electronic characteristics. Especially in the b -direction one might expect a semiconductor metal junction within the flake, which could lead to rectifying behavior or possibly even emission of photons. However, in our experiment we did not observe any noteworthy phenomena except for a slight decrease in conductivity likely due to the formation of slight cracks in the intercalated area. Nevertheless, the fact that we achieve partial intercalation in such a controlled manner opens up various possibilities for future experiments not only on fully, but also precisely partially intercalated devices.

Figure S14: (a) Pristine flake of CrSBr partially encapsulated in hBN (along b -direction) bottom contacted with gold contacts. (b) Comparison of pristine and partially intercalated flake after 2h of intercalation. Intercalation is visible up to the middle of the flake as confirmed by Raman map. (c) I - V sweep of pristine and intercalated flake. Except for a slight decrease in current, no major change was observed. (d) Gradual progression of intercalation along the b -direction over time.

Supplementary Section 6. Diffusion Experiments.

The intercalation length (L) at different times t was measured in ImageJ and plotted in Figure S15 against t . Two measurements in either direction per timestep were used to get a more accurate result. A crease in the top hBN layer was used as a reference point for the diffusion length for the diffusion in the a -direction. This assumes that the crease acts as a bottleneck for the diffusion into the rest of the sheet, with a constant concentration of Li^+ before the crease, allowing us to study the direction dependent diffusion kinetics beyond the crease. For the diffusion in the b -direction,

which branches off perpendicularly from the diffusion path in the a -direction, the diffusion length from the reference point was considered the starting value for the diffusion in the b -direction.

Perfect 1D diffusion can be described by the equation $L^2 = 2Dt$ (here L^2 is equivalent to the mean squared displacement (MSD)). Thus, we expect a linear relation between L^2 and t . However, the data shows two distinct regimes for all the datasets: a slow diffusion at first, followed by a faster one. We fit both regimes of L^2 vs. t for each dataset with a linear function and obtain two diffusion coefficients for each dataset from the slope of each fit $D = \frac{dL^2}{2dt}$. All fits are shown in Figure S15b-e with 95% confidence intervals for the fit. The measurement error was set as $0.513 \mu\text{m}$, which was the approximate uncertainty when measuring the diffusion length from the optical micrograph. Overall, the fit works reasonably well, the sudden change in diffusion coefficient mid experiment is likely due to a sudden change in cell parameters, which allows Li^+ to diffuse faster. Such sudden stepwise changes in diffusion are also observed in other materials.^[9]

While this is likely not a perfect description of the process, because of how L_0 was set, we can still use it to get an approximate value for the diffusion coefficients in each direction and calculate an anisotropy ratio which can later be compared with theoretical predictions. From the fits we calculate and average diffusion coefficient in either direction of $D_{a,1} = 9.0 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and $D_{b,1} = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ for the first regime and $D_{a,2} = 2.9 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and $D_{b,2} = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ for the second regime. By calculating the anisotropy ratio for each regime, we calculate an average of $\frac{D_a}{D_b} \approx 21.8 \pm 1.1$. The value for the b -direction is close to the reported Li ion diffusion coefficient in graphene of $D = 1.12 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ at 25°C and 0 state of charge.^[10] The ratio of anisotropy is close to other anisotropic materials such as GeP, where the ratio is 25.^[9]

Figure S15. (a) Intercalation process within covered flake without annotation. (b-e) Fit for each dataset. Left: L vs. t , right: L^2 vs. t . For regimes with 4 data points or more the 95% confidence interval is shown. Each datapoint is shown with error bars corresponding to a measurement uncertainty of 0.3 micron and 1s. (f) Combined data without subtraction of L_0 and t_0 .

Supplementary Section 7. Li diffusion from *ab initio* simulations.

1. Li intercalation

To simulate Li-intercalated CrSBr, we use a $(3 \times 2 \times 2)$ supercell based on the entry 175897 in the ICSD database^[11] (see also entry mp-22998 in the Materials Project database^[12]), containing 72

atoms per cell with the composition $\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$. Li atoms are placed at the remaining $2b$ (Cr) sites. We introduce 8 Li atoms into the supercell, yielding the composition $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$, which corresponds to 11% Li intercalation in CrSBr. Figure S16a-c shows the pristine CrSBr ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) supercell, while Figure S16d-f depicts the Li-intercalated supercell, where 8 of the 24 available $2b$ sites are occupied by Li.

Atomic positions and lattice vectors are relaxed using the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) algorithm as implemented in the QUANTUM ESPRESSO package.^[13] We adopt the PBEsol exchange-correlation functional^[14], include van der Waals interactions via Grimme’s DFT-D3 dispersion correction^[15], and perform spin-polarized calculations due to the presence of Cr atoms. After testing various k-point samplings^[16], we select Γ -point-only sampling, given the large size of the supercell.

Table S1 reports the lattice parameters and cell angles of the relaxed Li-intercalated CrSBr ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) supercell. For comparison, we also include the relaxed lattice parameters and angles for a ($1 \times 1 \times 1$) CrSBr cell, calculated using a ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) Monkhorst–Pack k-point grid^[16], alongside corresponding experimental values.^[17] Li intercalation leads to structural changes at the Li sites, including a reduction in z -buckling within the Cr–S–Cr–S chains along the y -direction (Figure S16), accompanied by a 4% decrease in the c -axis and a 3% increase in the b -axis (Table S1).

Figure S16. Pristine (a, b, c) and Li-intercalated (d, e, f) ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) supercells of CrSBr, containing 72 atoms (formula: $\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$) and 80 atoms (formula: $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$), respectively; (a) and (d): top views (ab plane); (b) and (e): side views (bc plane), (c) and (f): side views (ac plane). Li atoms are displayed in green, Cr atoms in blue, S atoms in yellow, and Br atoms in brown. Images are generated by VESTA software.^[18]

	CrSBr	CrSBr (experiments [7])	LiCrSBr ($3 \times 2 \times 2$)
a (Å)	3.56	3.50	10.53
b (Å)	4.71	4.74	9.74
c (Å)	7.75	7.91	14.88
α (deg)	90.0	90.0	89.96
β (deg)	90.0	90.0	90.08
γ (deg)	90.0	90.0	90.02

Table S1. Cell geometry (lattice parameters and angles) of the fully relaxed ($1 \times 1 \times 1$) cell of CrSBr (6 atoms per cell, formula: $\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_2\text{Br}_2$) using a ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) k-points Monkhorst-Pack grid^[16], together with the corresponding experimental values^[17] (first two columns, respectively). In the third column, the lattice parameters and angles of the LiCrSBr ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) supercell with 8 Li atoms (formula: $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$, see Fig. S13), fully relaxed at Γ , are reported. The latter is the supercell used for the AIMD simulations reported in this work.

2. Details of the *ab initio* Molecular Dynamics (AIMD) simulations

We perform *ab initio* Born–Oppenheimer molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations^[19], based on Kohn–Sham DFT^[20,21] within the plane-wave pseudopotential framework^[19,22], as implemented in the PW code of the QUANTUM ESPRESSO package.^[13] Simulations are carried out in the canonical (*NVT*) ensemble using a stochastic velocity rescaling thermostat.^[23]

We focus on four elevated temperatures (600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K), aiming to extrapolate Li diffusion down to room temperature. To account for the finite-temperature effects of Li intercalation on the cell volume and shape, we first perform a variable-cell (*NPT*) simulation at each temperature for ~ 10 ps. The thermally equilibrated supercells obtained from these *NPT* runs are then used in the subsequent *NVT* simulations. Figure S17 shows the total energies and instantaneous temperatures of the $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ supercell during the *NVT* dynamics.

Figure S17. Energies (a-d) and temperatures (e-h) for $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ in the NVT simulations: a), e): 600 K; b), f): 800 K; c), g): 1000 K; d), h): 1200 K.

3. Li trajectories

In Figure S18a-b, we show the initial (a) and final (b) snapshots of the simulation at 600 K, projected onto the ab (top), bc (center), and ac (bottom) planes. The trajectory lines highlight the paths of Li ions and illustrate Li mobility, revealing a pronounced diffusion anisotropy along the a -direction. We verified that no other species exhibit mobility over the temperature range studied (see Figure S19). Supplementary Videos S1a-b, S2a-b, and S3a-b show the AIMD trajectories at 600, 800, and 1000 K, respectively (a: projections on the xz -plane; b: projections on the yz -plane). Li atoms are depicted in green, each accompanied by a black trajectory line representing its path throughout the simulation. These visualizations clearly capture the diffusive behavior of the Li atoms, as well as the occurrence of individual atomic jumps during the dynamics. Li atoms easily jump on straight lines (channels) along the x -direction, with rarer off-channel jumps following a zig-zag pattern along yz that become more important at higher temperatures (800 and 1000 K).

Figure S18. (a) The 11% Li-intercalated (3 x 2 x 2) supercell of CrSBr (Li₈Cr₂₄S₂₄Br₂₄) used for the AIMD simulations, projected on the *ab* (top), *bc* (center), and *ac* (bottom) planes. Li atoms are displayed in green, Cr atoms in blue, S atoms in yellow, and Br atoms in brown. (b) Final snapshot (*t* ~ 40 ps) of the Li₈Cr₂₄S₂₄Br₂₄ supercell, projected on the *ab* (top), *bc* (center), and *ac* (bottom) planes, from the 600 K AIMD simulations. Trajectory lines are displayed to visualize the Li paths. Images are obtained by using OVITO.^[16]

4. Li mean squared displacements and diffusion coefficients

The mean squared displacement (MSD) of a given species provides a quantitative measure of its mobility within the material and is directly related to the self-diffusion coefficient. According to the Einstein relation for diffusion^[24–26], the self-diffusion coefficient for the Li species in three dimensions is given by:

$$D_i^{\text{Li}} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{6} \frac{d}{dt} \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \quad (\text{S3})$$

where the Li mean squared displacement $\text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t)$ for a system of N_{Li} atoms beyond the ballistic regime and over a sufficiently long time t is^[26]:

$$\text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{Li}}} \sum_i^{N_{\text{Li}}} |\mathbf{R}_i(t) - \mathbf{R}_i(0)|^2 \quad (\text{S4})$$

Here, $\mathbf{R}_i(t)$ is the instantaneous position of the i -th Li atom, and $|\mathbf{R}_i(t) - \mathbf{R}_i(0)|^2$ is the squared displacement from its initial position.

Figure S19a–d presents $\text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t)$ as computed from Eq. S4, alongside the MSDs for the other species—Cr, S, and Br—denoted as $\text{MSD}^{\text{Cr}}(t)$, $\text{MSD}^{\text{S}}(t)$, $\text{MSD}^{\text{Br}}(t)$, respectively. These results confirm that Li is the only mobile species across all temperatures considered.

Figure S19e–h shows both $\text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t)$ and the individual squared displacements $|\mathbf{R}_i(t) - \mathbf{R}_i(0)|^2$ for each Li atom in the simulation cell, at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K.

Figure S19. (a), (b), (c), (d): Mean squared displacements of the Li, Cr, S, and Br species in $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ derived from Eq. S4 at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K, respectively; (e), (f), (g), (h): Squared displacements of the single Li atoms in $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K, respectively; (i), (j), (k), (l): x, y, and z components of the Li mean square displacement in $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K, respectively.

Although AIMD simulations are highly accurate, they are limited to short time scales and small supercells^[19], thus, even in diffusive regimes, they cannot provide a reliable diffusion coefficient from Eq.S3. Consequently, it is common practice to replace Eq.S3 with the time-averaged formulation of the Einstein relation^[26–28].

$$D_i^{\text{Li}} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{6} \frac{d}{dt} \langle \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \rangle \quad (\text{S5})$$

Here, $\langle \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \rangle$ is obtained by performing a statistical average over initial times t' in the trajectory, leading to the following expression for the mean squared displacement:

$$\langle \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{N_{\text{Li}}} \sum_i^{N_{\text{Li}}} \langle |\mathbf{R}_i(t' + t) - \mathbf{R}_i(t')|^2 \rangle \quad (\text{S6})$$

We report the averaged $\langle \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \rangle$ from the simulations at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K in Figure S20. To evaluate the anisotropy of Li diffusion quantitatively, we extract the x -, y -, and z -components of $\langle \text{MSD}^{\text{Li}}(t) \rangle$ from the AIMD trajectories, which are shown in Figure S21a–c, d–f, g–i, and j–l for 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K, respectively. Figure S21a–b shows a $D_x^{\text{Li}}/D_y^{\text{Li}}$ ratio (with D_x^{Li} and D_y^{Li} derived from Eq. S5 of 20.8 ± 7.2 , in good agreement with the experimental results, as well as a $D_x^{\text{Li}}/D_z^{\text{Li}}$ ratio of approximately 40. A pronounced temperature dependence of the $D_x^{\text{Li}}/D_y^{\text{Li}}$ ratio is observed across the datasets: the ratio decreases from 20.8 ± 7.2 at 600 K to 6.5 ± 3.3 at 800 K, 5.9 ± 2.2 at 1000 K, and 4.4 ± 1.2 at 1200 K (Figure S21). Interestingly, the most significant reduction occurs between 600 and 800 K, suggesting the existence of two distinct diffusion regimes: one below 600–800 K, where Li predominantly migrates through x -oriented channels, and one above 600–800 K, where diffusion through y -oriented channels becomes accessible.

Figure S20. Li mean squared displacements averaged over the initial times (Eq. S6), from the 600 K (a), 800 K (b), 1000 K (c), and 1200 K (d) simulations. In each plot, the diffusion coefficient at that temperature derived from Eq. S5 is reported in the bottom panel.

Figure S21. Components along the x , y , and z -directions of the Li mean square displacement averaged over the initial times (Eq. S4), from the AIMD simulations at 600 K (a, b, and c, respectively), 800 K (d, e, and f, respectively), 1000 K (g, h, and i, respectively), and 1200 K (j, k, and l, respectively). In each plot, the direction-resolved diffusion coefficient at that temperature is reported in the bottom panel. From these, we extract values for the D_x/D_y ratio of 20.8, 6.5, 5.9, and 4.4 at 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K, respectively.

Finally, we treat Li diffusion as an activated process that follows an Arrhenius-type behavior^[29]:

$$\ln D^{\text{Li}}(T) = \ln A - \frac{E_{a_D^{\text{Li}}}}{k_B T} \quad (\text{S7})$$

In this expression, A is a pre-exponential factor related to the attempt frequency, and E_{aD}^{Li} represents the activation energy barrier for Li diffusion. The Arrhenius plot for D^{Li} is presented in Figure S22 in the conventional form $\log_{10} D^{\text{Li}}$ versus $1000/T$. From this analysis, we estimate the extrapolated Li diffusion coefficient at 300 K to be approximately $6.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$.

Figure S22. Arrhenius plot for Li diffusivity in $\text{Li}_8\text{Cr}_{24}\text{S}_{24}\text{Br}_{24}$ from the AIMD simulations, with the x , y , and z components of the diffusivity. Below 600 K, lines are drawn to obtain an estimate of the diffusion coefficient at 300 K ($\sim 6.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$). Corresponding activation energies are presented in the inset.

Supplementary Section 8. Magnetic properties.

To satisfy the requirements for SQUID magnetometry, Li-CrSBr was prepared by horn sonication of bulk CrSBr, isolated by centrifugation, and subsequently dried and intercalated overnight with lithium anthracenide under inert conditions (see the details in Methods). Intercalated sample was drop-casted onto an Si/SiO₂ substrate to investigate its optical appearance and confirm intercalation by probing Raman spectra. Optical imaging of Li-CrSBr revealed ribbon-like exfoliated flakes with various thicknesses of tens to hundreds of layers (Figure S23a). Raman spectra probed from flakes marked in the optical image confirmed the intercalation, showing characteristic for Li-CrSBr A_1^1, A_1^2, A_1^3 modes at 95 cm^{-1} , 225 cm^{-1} , and 331 cm^{-1} , respectively, as shown Figure S23b.

The Zero-Field-Cooled and Field-Cooled (ZFC-FC) susceptibility study of the Li-intercalated and pristine CrSBr, shown in Figure S23c, reveals a striking difference between the two samples. Both the ZFC and FC curves of CrSBr coincide and show a clear anomaly at around 134 K, which indicates the onset of antiferromagnetic ordering and corresponds to its Néel temperature. In contrast, the susceptibility of the Li intercalation product reveals an establishment of ferromagnetic order upon cooling below the critical temperature of $\approx 190 \text{ K}$.

The low-temperature magnetization curves, depicted in Figure S24, confirm the difference between the samples. The anhysteretic response of CrSBr provides a high-field magnetization of $108 \text{ A m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$, which is equivalent to $3.16 \mu_B$ per Cr atom in alignment with its oxidation state. The Li-intercalated sample exhibits hysteresis with a coercivity of $\mu_0 H_c = 0.15 \text{ T}$ and is characterized by magnetization of spontaneous ordering of $73 \text{ A m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$, the latter suggesting the presence of some diamagnetic component. Considering that the field-cooled hysteresis loop is not affected by exchange bias (see Figure S24c), the presence of crystallites containing both ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic regions is rather unlikely.

Focusing our attention on the paramagnetic region of the samples far above the Néel and Curie temperatures, interesting insight into both systems is obtained by fitting the inverse magnetic susceptibility according to the equation: $\chi^{-1} = \left(\chi_{\text{TI}} + \frac{C}{T - \theta_{\text{CW}}} \right)^{-1}$, which combines a temperature-independent term χ_{TI} (involving the diamagnetic response of the plastic capsule as well diamagnetic components of the sample) and the Curie-Weiss law with the Curie constant C and the Weiss constant θ_{CW} . The analysis of the CrSBr phase leads to a positive Weiss constant $\theta_{\text{CW}} = 172 \text{ K}$, evidencing rather strong ferromagnetic interaction. This value, characterizing a polycrystalline material, matches well with the data reported on a single CrSBr crystal: $\theta_{\text{CW}} = 185, 164,$ and 184 K for measurements along $a, b,$ and c axes.^[30] Similar analysis for the Li-intercalated system shows even stronger ferromagnetic interaction leading to $\theta_{\text{CW}} = 208 \text{ K}$. The intercalation is accompanied by doping with itinerant electrons that enhance the ferromagnetism in individual layers through the double exchange mechanism.^[31]

Figure S23. The optical images (a) and Raman spectra (b) of Li-CrSBr liquid-phase-exfoliated flakes. Static magnetic susceptibility as a function of temperature (c), measured in the ZFC and FC regimes using a probe field of 10 mT.

Figure S24. Magnetization curves at 2 K. (a) Full hysteresis loops of the Li-intercalated sample and the pristine CrSBr, the inset shows the detail at lower magnetic fields up to 0.5 T. (b) Virgin curve of the Li-intercalate and analogous M - H data for the pristine CrSBr, the dashed line shows the linearization of the high-field region, providing spontaneous magnetization of $73 \text{ A m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ for the intercalated sample and magnetization of $108 \text{ A m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ for CrSBr. (c) Comparison of the hysteresis loops of the Li-CrSBr after cooling in zero magnetic field and in field of 7 T.

Supplementary Section 9. Additional Time Dependent Conductivity Measurements.

Figure S25 shows a characterization of a simple two-terminal device based on a few layered sheets of CrSBr (~ 9 layers, see Figure 25b) before and after intercalation as well as after 15 h of exposure to ambient conditions. During the intercalation, a slight change in color becomes visible, and after 15 h on air, small dark spots can be seen at the device edges, which are likely caused by lithium exiting the sheet and forming lithium salts when reacting with air. The Raman measurements shown in Figure 25c confirm the intercalation of the sheet indicated by the emergence of A_1^1 , A_1^2 , and A_1^3 modes at around 17 cm^{-1} , 16 cm^{-1} , and 7 cm^{-1} lower energies than the pristine modes respectively. During 15 h in ambient conditions, the original peaks return, indicating a slow deintercalation, however, they never quite reach the position of the non-intercalated material. An offset of 1.5 cm^{-1} remains, as well as a slight shoulder of the A_g^2 peak, at this point the sheet is most likely still slightly intercalated but to a much lesser extent as it had been initially. In this device substantial contact resistance and Schottky behavior was observed even in the pristine measurement, as a result the increase in conductivity is higher than in the device in Figure 5 of the main text, around one order of magnitude. In fact, the contacts appear to be improving, indicated by the higher linearity and steeper curve in the low bias regime. In the high bias regime, we still observe the same trend of gradual decrease in conductivity associated with the deintercalation of Li and corresponding reduction in charge carrier density.

Figure S25: (a) Optical micrograph of one CrSBr device in a pristine state, intercalated, and after exposure to ambient conditions for 15 h. (b) AFM plot of the CrSBr device with height profile as an inset. The thickness of the devices is ca. 8 nm corresponding to 9 layers. (c) Raman spectra of the device in a pristine state, intercalated, and after exposure to ambient conditions for 15 h. (d) Output characteristics of the device in a pristine state, intercalated, and after exposure to ambient conditions for 15 h. The inset shows the highly linear low bias regime. (e) Continuous conductivity measurement during the exposure to ambient conditions with $V_{DS} = 1$ V. The left axis shows the current during the measurement and the right the sheet resistance R_s .

Figure S26a shows the output current extracted from repeated I - V sweeps during the first 40 minutes after intercalation of the experiment in section 2.3 of the main manuscript. Figure S26b-c shows the corresponding I - V curves during this initial phase of the experiment.

Figure S26: (a) Output current extracted from repeated I - V sweeps at a bias of 1V during the first 40 minutes of the experiment in section 2.3 of the main manuscript. Corresponding I - V sweeps for the a -direction (b) and b -direction (c).

Figures S27 and S28 show additional long term stability experiments in an inert atmosphere. One device was prepared for each crystal direction and the devices were measured using repeated I - V sweeps before and after intercalation in the same way as the device in section 2.3 of the main manuscript. However, in this case we do not expose the devices to air, instead we keep them in an argon atmosphere for the whole duration of the experiment. The optical micrographs and Raman spectra are shown in Figure S27a-b and Figure S28a-b respectively. In both cases these confirm that the flakes remain intercalated. The output current extracted from the I - V sweeps at an applied source-drain bias of 1 V is plotted in Figure S27c for the a -direction device and Figure S28c for the b -direction device. The immediate effect of intercalation on the electrical properties of both devices is similar to the device in section 2.3 of the main manuscript, with a slight increase in output current for the measurement along a -direction and a decrease along b -direction (although more substantial in this case). However, without exposure to air, the performance remains stable over a duration of 10 days, showing no signs of deintercalation or gradual decrease in current.

Figure S27: (a) Optical micrographs of CrSBr two-terminal device for measurement along the *a*-direction before intercalation, after intercalation, and after 10 days in an argon atmosphere. (b) Raman spectra of the device before intercalations, after intercalation, and after 10 days in an argon atmosphere. (c) Output current extracted from repeated *I*-*V* sweeps at an applied source drain bias of 1 V.

Figure S28: (a) Optical micrographs of CrSBr two-terminal device for measurement along the *b*-direction before intercalations, after intercalation, and after 12 days in an argon atmosphere. (b) Raman spectra of the device before intercalations, after intercalation, and after 12 days in an argon atmosphere. (c) Output current extracted from repeated *I*-*V* sweeps at an applied source drain bias of 1 V.

the device before intercalations, after intercalation, and after 12 days in an argon atmosphere. (c) Output current extracted from repeated I - V sweeps at an applied source drain bias of 1 V.

Supplementary Section 10. Temperature Dependence of Conductivity.

Figure S29a shows the temperature dependence of conductivity of a few-layer sheet of Li-CrSBr in the a and b -direction and for reference also the a -direction of pristine CrSBr. The raised Fermi-level due to the extra charge carriers in Li-CrSBr should theoretically lead to metallic behavior at least in the b -direction^[30]. We observe an increase in conductivity by more than one order of magnitude for both directions; however, we still see thermally activated transport. Notably, we also observe a substantially faster drop in conductivity with decreasing temperature, compared to the pristine case, in all our measurements. It had previously been reported that bulk Li-CrSBr shows a feature around 200 K which suggests the onset of ferromagnetic ordering. As our initial measurement shows a measurement artefact (related to switching of the preamplifier) in this region, we repeated the measurement with a two terminal device only along the a -direction. As shown in Figure S29b this device shows a similarly steep decrease in conductivity, compared to the pristine device, but as shown in the inset there is a noticeable feature at around 235 K, which could be related to ferromagnetic ordering. Since we observe the feature both during the heating and cooling, it is likely a real feature, although it is 30 K higher than expected.

Figure S29. (a) Temperature dependence of CrSBr (a -direction) compared to Li-CrSBr (a and b -direction). Measured on the same sample (two sets of perpendicular contacts were used to contact the sheet). Room temperature conductivity is higher than in the pristine flake but drops fast with decreasing temperature. The sudden change between 200 and 250 K is a measurement artifact from switching the preamplifier during the measurement. Semi-transparent curves correspond to the noise floor. (b) Temperature dependence of CrSBr (a -direction) compared to Li-CrSBr (a -direction) measured on a different device. A simpler two contact geometry was used. A similar decrease in conductivity is observed. A feature is visible around 235 K which is likely related to ferromagnetic ordering. The inset shows the feature region more closely. Semi-transparent curves correspond to the noise floor.

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